

**DEVELOPING STUDENTS' GENERAL HUMAN VALUES COMPETENCY IN
THE NEW UZBEKISTAN EDUCATION CONDITIONS**

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Annotation: this article describes the content and analysis of the development of competence in students regarding universal values in the educational conditions of New Uzbekistan, in a time when the influence of various foreign ideas that have a negative effect on the human mind is increasing. , education, promotion and propaganda work in the development of students' competence in universal human values, through pedagogical means of developing high human qualities such as national, universal values, religious tolerance, patriotism, and the spirit of loyalty to the motherland illuminated.

Key words: national value, universal value, national tradition, traditions, patriotism, spirituality, national idea, propaganda, national pride, national pride, history ,

Today, the main goal of comprehensive reforms in the education system, the development of students' competence regarding universal human values, their importance in the development of the state and society is a constant research object of world scientists. In the Inchon Declaration of UNESCO, signed in South Korea until 2030, "Education is the main driving force of development and an important activity that achieves the goals of sustainable development ¹" and its main tasks include " history is the obligation to change lives , to educate people in a new way." It is not for nothing that it is recognized as a call for strong and innovative actions for the development of the country .

of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 "On measures for the further development of the higher education system", ²based on the priority tasks of the fundamental improvement of the higher education system and the socio-economic development of the country, the personnel training system was established. radical improvement indicates that great attention is paid to the quality of ensuring the creation of necessary conditions for the training of highly educated specialists at the level of international standards.

Emphasizing the complex, integral nature of competence in educational practice today, three levels or aspects of it are distinguished in the world community in educational management models :

- 1) integrative competence - the ability to acquire knowledge and skills and use them in the rapidly changing conditions of the external environment;
- 2) socio-psychological competence - intelligence, knowledge and skills to understand people's behavior, motivation of their work, high level of openness and communication culture.

¹ Obrazovanie 2030 Inchonskaya deklaration i ramohnaya programma deystviy .: Republic of Korea s 19 po 25 maya 2015 g.

² Resolution No. PQ2909 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 "On measures to further develop the higher education system"

3) competence in certain areas of management activity - decision-making, information gathering, methods of working with people, etc.

From the point of view of new socio-educational ideas, the concept of competence is developing further. One of the stages of competence development in a student is related to expanding the scope of its components by including additional areas of competence important for the subject's professional activity. Scientist J. Raven, who put forward the main ideas of the competent approach emphasizes the importance of this: "when we compare more and less competent teachers, drivers, blacksmiths, managers, and military officers, in each case the political behavior displayed by the masters of their work turns out to be the most important."

Because, in our republic, in parallel with the improvement of the continuous education system, special attention is being paid to the development of the competence of students regarding universal values in pedagogic education. "To study our values, spiritual-ethical, philosophical and pedagogical heritage, the history of the formation and development of public education from original sources, to enrich the scope of the theory and history of pedagogy based on objective data, to further expand the possibility of developing our pedagogical thinking methodological foundations were created³." In the conditions of the new Uzbekistan, the issue of developing the competence of students regarding universal values is accepted in our country in the "Strategy of Actions" for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and at the same time, an in-depth analysis of the development path of our country, today the world market is mine In the conditions of sudden changes in the industry, increasing competition in the conditions of globalization, the development and implementation of a completely new approach and principles for the development of our country at a more stable and rapid pace has been defined as a priority task⁴. As a result, the period studied in the researches related to the history of pedagogic teachings in the conditions of New Uzbekistan created a ground for the scientific study of issues such as the development of competence in students regarding universal values.

In today's rapidly developing era, despite the research work being carried out in the field of education and a number of positive changes achieved, in order to increase the effectiveness of the educational system, first of all, it is necessary to accelerate the dynamics of the development of education, to effectively use the conditions and opportunities created in it, to In the training of competitive specialists for educational institutions, the issue of educating a competent person based on their national values is of urgent importance.

A scientist psychologically defines competence as a criterion for understanding the surrounding world and the proportionality of interaction with it, or if it is defined in more detail, it is a set of knowledge, skills and abilities that allow the successful implementation of activities, or a person's ability to relate to the environment and development. It also touches on the main factors of mastering the methods of influencing people.

In particular, development of competence in students regarding universal human values rapidly developing the globalized and integrated world is rapidly changing, the negative influence of various foreign ideas is increasing in the processes of the young generation's awareness of

³Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 24, 2017 No. PQ-2995 "On measures to further improve the system of preservation, research and promotion of ancient written sources".

⁴Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T., 2017. No. 6.

national identity, loyalty to universal values, and the strengthening of individual spirituality, for people's minds and hearts in the era of intensifying ideological struggles, the importance of inculcating the spirit of loyalty to universal values in the educational process is increasing. In the spiritual life of the people, self-awareness plays an important role. Therefore, in the development of the competence of students regarding universal values, the same spiritual and moral education should be given special attention to the essence of national self-awareness, concepts of people, nation and their interrelationship. It is noted that it is necessary to pay attention. Analyzing the essence-logical aspect of the development of competence in students regarding universal human values, within the framework of the study of the research conducted by us, it is necessary to focus on the analysis of the scientific opportunities in the work of local and foreign researchers, focusing on competence, pedagogical ability. we found

LMDolgova, a foreign scientist ⁵, competence is the organization and implementation of activities based on acquired knowledge. Competence implies experience of independent activity based on universal knowledge. Competence is the presence of knowledge and skills in a socio-practical form, and it is recognized that it is manifested in cases where socio-cultural requirements are imposed by the society on the results of the educational process.

SEshishkov ⁶:

- general competence based on knowledge, experience, values and dispositions acquired through study;

the ability to make connections between knowledge and situations, and the importance of finding a problem-appropriate way of solving them.

EFZeer ⁷'s research, competence is a set of knowledge, skills, as well as methods of performing certain tasks in the individual's activity, which consists of the following components:

socio-legal competence - knowledge and skills in the field of social institutions and interpersonal activities, as well as thorough mastery of professional communication methods and rules of conduct;

special competence - readiness to independently carry out certain types of activities, the ability to solve common professional issues and evaluate the results of one's work, the ability to independently acquire new knowledge and skills in one's specialty ;

personal competence - the ability to constantly improve professional skills and qualifications, to show oneself in professional activities;

⁵Dolgova L.M. P robyne deystviya uchashchikhsya v prostanstve innovatsionnoy school . 2007. P.191-193.

1. ⁶ Shishkov S.E. [Monitoring kachestva obrazovatel'nogo protsessa v shkole /S.E.Shishiov, V.A.Kalniy.-M: Pedagogicheskoe obshchestvo Rossii, 1999. – 320 p.](#)

⁷Zeer E.F. Modernization of professional education: a competent approach // *Obrazovanie i nauka. Izvestia . Ural. otdeleni e RAO. 2004. – No. 3. – S. 42-53.*

self-competence - having a true vision of one's socio-professional capabilities, being able to overcome professional difficulties, explained aspects such as.

According to the scientist, professional competence can be seen in the following professional characteristics of a specialist:

– professional goal orientation of a person: striving for success and achievements, carrying out joint activities with the team and burning for the interests of the team, reliability, worthiness of one's profession, etc.;

– professionally important qualities: conscientiousness, ability to analyze one's mental state, independence, responsibility, intellectual maturity, ability to assess and predict, communicative, professional mobilization, ability to solve problems, etc.;

– occupationally important psychophysiological qualities: ability to work, ability to skillfully perform manual work, psychomotor skills, eye contact skills, etc.

Orientation of the educational process to the competency approach requires a review and development of methodological conditions in education, the content and application of new pedagogical technologies, because competencies do not refer to knowledge and skills in any subject. As traditional education focuses on the acquisition of a specific set of knowledge, skills and competencies by the learner, today, while acquiring in-depth knowledge, they can be applied when the need or opportunity arises. , you can meet people who can't use it at the right time and place.

Therefore , the methods and technologies of competence-oriented education should ensure the easy transfer and adaptability of abilities formed in certain conditions to other conditions, that is, they should create the characteristic of "non-adaptive activity". Therefore, the main goal of developing students' competence in universal values, educating young people in the spirit of creative ideas, loyalty to universal values, and educating them on the basis of their national values is important. Therefore, since the development of competence in students regarding universal values is recognized as the main factor, turning into self-confidence and faith, it is necessary to educate students as personnel who will burn their lives for the fate of the country in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland, national and universal values, and training values. not what he gave us, but what I did for the country!" defining the slogan as the main issue of one's professional and life activity is important.

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